

Including the Bottom Billion: Integrating Subsistence Economies into Integrated Assessment Modeling

Abstract

This study introduces *MORDRED* (Model of Regime Dynamics and Environmental Development), a system dynamics Integrated Assessment Model (IAMs) that incorporates a subsistence sector and migration flows between capitalist and non-capitalist regimes. By coupling demographic, economic, and biophysical variables, the model explores four scenarios of global development and environmental change: *Neoliberal Promises*, *Shadows of Neoliberal Development*, *Breakdown of Neoliberal Development*, and *High Adaptive Capacity of Subsistence Economies*. The results reveal dynamics of accumulation by dispossession, exploitation and contamination underpinning rural and urban economic development in the Global South. However, feedbacks between an expanding global economy characterized by high inequality, and a destabilized Earth system also can destabilize the global accumulation regime and revert the direction of rural-urban migration. Thus, while *Neoliberal Promises* replicates the narrative of smooth urbanization and growth benefitting all, other scenarios expose the instability of neoliberal development under growing biophysical constraints, culminating in potential economic collapse and partial 'ruralization'. The findings emphasize the need to expand the scope of IAMs by representing socio-economic (re)production through subsistence and informal economies in order to arrive at more holistic assessment of impacts, vulnerabilities, adaptation and mitigation centered on poverty eradication, need-based production and resilience.

Keywords

Subsistence, Global South, smallholders, scenarios, climate change, migration.

1. Introduction

Despite the ongoing expansion of global capitalism, reflected in dynamics of ‘planetary urbanization’ (Brenner & Schmid, 2015) and continuously advancing commodity frontiers (Barbesgaard & Whitmore, 2024; Meyfroidt et al., 2024; Moore, 2000), there remain approximately 66 million pastoralists (Jenet et al., 2017), 476 million indigenous people (World Bank, 2025a) and up to 2.5 billion people belonging to smallholder farm households (Peck et al., 2013) who live at the margins of the global accumulation regime.

As these groups depend directly on the environment for survival, they are highly vulnerable to the adverse effects of environmental change and degradation (Albore et al., 2024; Gatew & Guyo, 2024; Hazarika et al., 2024; Nori et al., 2008; Widiono et al., 2024). Simultaneously, Indigenous, pastoralist, and peasant cultures and livelihoods face socio-economic threats stemming from unrestrained capitalist development linked to extended urbanization. This manifests, for example, through land grabbing in the name of rural or urban development, often backed or enforced by the state (Khan & Karak, 2018; Pratama et al., 2021; Whiting, 2022). Although accelerating the global energy transition is necessary to achieve climate goals, the large-scale deployment of renewable energy technologies risks further exacerbating these pressures through ‘renewables grabbing’ (Scheidel et al., 2023), particularly given the strong overlap between Indigenous and peasant lands and mining projects for energy transition minerals (Owen et al., 2022). The vulnerability of these socio-economic groups to adverse environmental changes is thus mediated by the political economy of global capitalism (Bernards, 2025; Ford, 2012).

In other words, although many Indigenous, pastoralist, and peasant communities live at or beyond the margins of the capitalist system they are not insulated from its dynamics. Focusing on the poorest smallholder farmers, at least three mechanisms link global capitalist development to the future of rural subsistence regimes.

First, capitalism has expanded through primitive accumulation, i.e. the expropriation of rural populations and the integration of their territories; comparable contemporary processes have been termed *accumulation by dispossession* (Harvey, 2003). Although the widespread and often interchangeable use of these concepts has been problematized (Glassman, 2006; Hall, 2013; Raju Das, 2017), both draw attention to how capitalist outward expansion secures the cheap environmental inputs (food, energy and raw materials) required for surplus value creation (Moore, 2015, 2017).

Second, primitive accumulation produces property-less workers who can be put to work for capital, resulting in *accumulation by exploitation* (Bonefeld, 2023). Cheap labor-power complements material inputs and is reproduced through rural-urban migration, where migrants swell the industrial reserve army and inadvertently contribute to the cheapening of the labor force (Li, 2020). However, in many countries, limited industrialization has given rise to a distinct form of urbanization characterized by discontinuous and contested metabolic configurations, persistent mismatches between capital and labor, an inflated informal economy and high vulnerability among urban residents (Parida & Agrawal, 2023; Schindler, 2017). The mismatch between migrants’ skills and formal employment opportunities, combined with rapid urbanization and insufficient levels industrialization, results in the de facto exclusion of these ‘marginalized of the wasteland’ from spaces of capitalist production and valorization who – in contrast to Marx’s reserve army of labor – face little chances of being incorporated into wage-labor-based production (Khan & Karak, 2018; Sanyal, 2007; Zhang et al., 2023)

Third, *accumulation by contamination* describes global ecological cost-shifting, whereby profit-maximizing activities degrade, contaminate and pollute ecosystems across the world, resulting in environmental injustice (D'Alisa & Demaria, 2024; Demaria, 2015). It can co-occur with accumulation by dispossession, for instance when waste treatment is financialized and privatized: large-scale incineration can create health-risks for residents while depriving waste pickers of recyclable materials (D'Alisa & Demaria, 2024). Climate change and toxic waste from fossil extraction constitute paradigmatic examples (Picard & Beigi, 2020).

At the same time, populations at the margins of the global economy are not merely passive victims but possess adaptive agency and may play key roles in mitigating anthropogenic environmental pressures as they often coexist with their surrounding ecosystems (Samberg et al., 2016). Smallholder farmers, pastoralists, and Indigenous communities can support carbon sequestration, fire prevention, and biodiversity conservation while sustaining their livelihoods (Ewing et al., 2023; Jenet et al., 2017; Negash & Kanninen, 2015; Nikolakis et al., 2022; Nori et al., 2008; Soto-Pinto et al., 2010). They also retain valuable local knowledge relevant for observing local climatic changes (Chanza & Musakwa, 2022; Savo et al., 2016) and developing socio-ecological systems more resilient to shocks (Altieri & Koohafkan, 2008; Caviedes et al., 2024; Estrada et al., 2022).

Despite the complex dynamics, the 'bottom billion'—those most excluded from industrial capitalist development—remain largely absent from global scenario exercises exploring potential socio-environmental futures (Lauer, Carpintero, et al., 2025; Lauer, Llases, et al., 2025). Quantitatively, Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) generally fail to represent economies apart from the global 'market economy', leaving them blind to the mitigation potential of subsistence systems, and to how economic growth and environmental degradation jointly affect marginalized ways of life. Although IAMs quantify environmental policies such as carbon pricing, they are poorly equipped to address structural or systemic alternatives, such as food sovereignty (Saghai, 2021). To date, no IAM has modeled the different manifestations of capitalist accumulation shaping rural-urban migration and development trajectories. Instead, models rely on classical development economics' assumptions of smooth, industrialization-led urbanization and wage differentials producing an 'urban pull' on the rural population (Khan & Karak, 2018; Li, 2020). For example, in some widely used socio-economic scenarios between 80% (SSP2 and LED) and 92% (SSP1 and SSP5) of the world population is assumed to live in cities by 2100 (Bluwstein & Cavanagh, 2023). Consequently, although IAMs aim to analyze the drivers of environmental change, its impacts on vulnerable populations and possible mitigation and adaptation options (IPCC, 2023), their neglect of economies at or beyond capitalist frontiers likely results in incomplete or biased insights.

This article takes a first step toward addressing this gap by presenting and exploring an IAM that represents key relationships between the global capitalist economy and rural subsistence regimes. We pursue three research objectives. First, we demonstrate the feasibility of modeling economic structures outside the capitalist economy by integrating a simple 'subsistence economy' into an IAM. Second, we wish to explore different conceivable futures for the world's poorest under different capitalist development pathways. Last, we are interested in the associated demographic, economic and environmental consequences of these scenarios.

2. Methods

2.1. MORDRED model

Given that a detailed description of MORDRED, including data sources, calculations and relevant model equations, is provided in the model's documentation (Lauer & Llases, 2025), we only provide a brief overview of the model's structure below, focusing on the representation of the subsistence sector and its interactions with the global economy.

2.1.1. General model characteristics

MORDRED is a system-dynamics based, environmentally and socially extended global input-output model with 25 sectors, coupled with a climate, land, energy and population model. The economic model projects future changes in private and public consumption, investment, capital stock and the production of intermediate products, based on exogenously fixed target consumption growth rates. Technological developments—such as changes in energy intensities, the electricity mix, material extraction costs, or material efficiency—are captured through the A matrix, which changes endogenously as well as through exogenous scenario assumptions about future technological change.

The sector-specific demand for labor hours can be met with the labor hours provided by the population that lives fully integrated in the world economy. To survive, the population in the working age (15 – 64 years), which is assumed to sustain the rest of the population, is willing to engage in global productive processes. While the maximum supply of labor hours is determined by the size of the population in the working age and by their capacity to work –influenced by the participation rate and by heat-related climate damages – the allocation of the working force between sectors depends on the extent of sector-specific industry and final demand, which in turn depends on the purchasing power of different classes.

Within the global economy, there are 9 social classes with different consumption levels which, in the initial moment of the simulation, depend on estimates about global consumption inequality, and during the simulations change according to scenario assumptions. Three classes reside in the world region 'center' that includes all high-income countries. They are derived by dividing the population into the richest 20%, the poorest 30% and the remaining 50%. The next three classes are constituted by the population of the 'semiperiphery' which consists of all upper-middle-income countries, according to the world bank's (2025b) country classification. The last three classes are part of the 'periphery' that contains all lower-middle- and low-income countries. They are derived in the same way as the classes of the center. Age-specific birth and death rates within the global economy are influenced by the different per capita consumption levels per class and region. While all 20 age groups represented in the model (0-4 years, 5-9 years, ... 95+ years) have age-specific mortality rates, only the 15- to 44-year-olds have age-specific birth rates.

The demand of global economic production for different land types (mainly forests, cropland and pastures, infrastructure, land for energy generation), and land availability are determined in the land module. The demand and supply of different types of energy is calculated in the energy module, while environmental impacts from economic activities are depicted in the 'environmental stressors' and the 'climate' modules.

The simultaneous representation of various dimensions of the global socio-economic and environmental system, and their integration into one comprehensive model, renders MORDRED an IAM of medium complexity. Nevertheless, the modeling logic of MORDRED differs from that of

most existing IAMs (for exceptions see Capellán-Pérez et al. (2020); Mediavilla et al. (2025)) due to the following characteristics: First, the model can represent scarcity of several production factors necessary for economic activities (labor, land, energy, intermediate products), and the consequences of rising scarcity for economic development pathways, including a decline or reversal of economic growth. Second, the model integrates various feedback dynamics between different parts of the model, such as the influence of consumption levels on demographic parameters, and the influence of demographic changes on labor availability. Third, the model represents several channels through which adverse climate change impacts driven by rising global average temperatures can deteriorate the conditions of economic production.

2.1.2. Representation of the subsistence sector

The subsistence economy is represented through a separation of three modules – the demographic, the land and the economic modules - into two spheres, i.e. the global or formal mode of (re)production and the subsistence mode of (re)production.

In the demographic module, in every world region, the population is divided into two segments. The larger segment is assumed to be fully integrated into the world economy, i.e., they sustain the global economy through their labor and are in turn sustained by the output of global production processes. The smaller segment is assumed to live and work in a subsistence economy at the margins of the world economy, with only occasional points of interaction.

In 2020, more than 700 million people lived in extreme poverty in 2020 (UN DESA, 2023) while the estimated number of smallholder farms with a size of 2-5 ha ranges between 380 million (Samberg et al., 2016) and 510 million (Lowder et al., 2025), sustaining between 1.5 and 2.5 billion people (Peck et al., 2013). Focusing on the high intersection between the poorest subsistence farming households and the population living in extreme poverty (Lowder et al., 2025), we set the number of people belonging to the subsistence economy to 800 million in the initial moment of the simulation, divided between the semiperiphery (15%) and the periphery (85%).

The population participating in the subsistence economy features high but constant fertility and mortality rates that correspond to a constant per capita consumption of which only the equivalent of 729 (2019-)€/year, i.e. the consumption under extreme poverty, is monetized in the global economy. Thus, fertility and mortality in subsistence are not influenced by changing per capita consumption in the global economy.

Migration movements between the subsistence and the formal economy in every world region depend on the difference in consumption per capita levels (Cpc) between the poorest class ($P30$) in the respective world region, and the subsistence class. The higher the difference in consumption, the higher the share of the population willing to leave the subsistence regime (sub) and integrate into the world economic regime (we). Equation (1) represents the region- (r) and age- (a) specific migration rate, i.e. the share of the subsistence population that wants to migrate, while equation (2) calculates the absolute region- and age-specific migration flow from the subsistence to the world economy, based on the population living in subsistence at a given moment of the simulation (P^{sub}), and the maximum population size that can be sustained through the cultivation of subsistence land ($MaxP^{sub}$). If the land that is used by the subsistence regime is reduced, the maximum population size decreases. Thus, under certain conditions, dynamics of a forced integration into the world economy can emerge, fueled for instance by accumulation through dispossession or accumulation by contamination.

$$Mr_r^{sub \rightarrow we} = \max \left(0, \min \left(0.1; \beta 1 \cdot (Cpc_{r,P30}^{we} - Cpc^{sub}) \right) \right) \quad (1)$$

$$M_{r,a}^{sub \rightarrow we} = \max \left(Mr_r^{sub \rightarrow we} \cdot P_{r,a}^{sub}; \left(\frac{\max(0; P^{sub} - MaxP^{sub})}{P^{sub}} \right) \cdot P_{r,a}^{sub} \right) \quad (2)$$

The representation of migration flows from the subsistence sector to the world economy can be used to explore accumulation by exploitation dynamics that occur when the world economy absorbs cheap labor from the subsistence regime. However, MORDRED also allows a reversal of this dynamic, i.e. reintegration into the subsistence regime. Within each region and social class (cl), the share of people that want to leave the world economy ($Mr_{r,cl}^{we \rightarrow sub}$) grows as the consumption levels in the global economy in any given class (cl) begin to approach those within the subsistence regime (3). The absolute migration flows depend on the maximum number of people that the subsistence regime can sustain in any given moment of time, and the size of the respective class (4).

$$Mr_{r,cl}^{we \rightarrow sub} = \max \left(0, \min \left(\beta 0 - \beta 1 \cdot Cpc_{r,cl}^{we}(time_step - 1) \right) \right) \quad (3)$$

$$M_{r,a}^{we \rightarrow sub} = \max \left(0; \min \left(1; \frac{MaxP^{sub} - P^{sub}}{\sum (Mr_{r,cl}^{we \rightarrow sub} \cdot P_{r,a}^{we} \cdot class_share_{cl})} \right) \right) \quad (4)$$

$$\cdot \sum_{cl} (Mr_{r,cl}^{we \rightarrow sub} \cdot P_{r,a}^{we} \cdot class_share_{cl})$$

In the land module, the land demand by the subsistence economy ($Land_{sub}^d$) depends on the number of people living in subsistence conditions, the people that want to leave the world economy and the subsistence land intensity ($Int_{sub}^{Land^d}$) (5). In the initial moment of time, the latter is given in km² per million people and is calculated based on the initial population that is working in the subsistence regime and the land managed per worker, estimated based on data on the farm size of African smallholders (Altieri & Koohafkan, 2008) (6). In turn, the maximum population that can be sustained in any moment of time depends on the land intensity and the land size of the subsistence regime in this moment of time (7). The demand of the global industrialized food sector for different types of land ($Land_{1,we}^d$) is calculated with sector-specific land intensities and the desired annual output of the food sector (X_1^d) (8).

Land intensity increases with global warming, reflecting a loss of land productivity due to climate change impacts such as extreme weather events (Altieri & Koohafkan, 2008; Aragón et al., 2021). For simplicity, it is assumed that land intensity increases as a linear function of changes in global average temperature compared to the pre-industrial period (9). The damage factor $a_{climate\ damage}$ can be changed in different scenario simulations, depending on the assumed resilience and adaptation capacity of the population sustaining the subsistence mode of production (Levene & Conversi, 2017; Thorlakson & Neufeldt, 2012; Touch et al., 2024). It reflects the consequences of ‘accumulation by contamination’ since the subsistence population faces a climate-change-induced loss in land productivity that is caused primarily by the greenhouse gases emissions of the global capitalist economy.

$$Land_{sub}^d = \sum_{r,a} (P_{r,a}^{sub} + M_{r,a}^{we \rightarrow sub}) \cdot Int_{sub}^{Land} \quad (5)$$

$$Int_{subt_0}^{Land} = \frac{Int_{sub\ worker}^{Land} \cdot workers_{subt_0}}{\sum_{r,a} (P_{r,a}^{sub})_{t_0}} \quad (6)$$

$$MaxP^{sub} = Land_{sub} \cdot Int_{sub}^{Land} \quad (7)$$

$$Land_{1,we}^d = \sum_i (X_1^d \cdot Int_{1,we}^{Land}) \quad (8)$$

$$Int_{sub}^{Land} = Int_{subt_0}^{Land} + a_{climate\ damage} \cdot (\Delta Temp_{1850} - 1) \quad (9)$$

If total land demand exceeds land supply, the model uses an allocation mechanism to prioritize different land demands, depending on the land priorities specified in the respective scenario. If land demand from the subsistence sector has a low priority, the amount of subsistence land shrinks and is integrated into the world economy. This dynamic reflects accumulation by dispossession. Other cases of dispossession, e.g. by the expansion of material extraction activities, are not directly modeled in MORDRED. However, changes in the amount of materials extracted, which are tracked by the model, can serve as indicators for extraction-related land conflicts.

The input-output data describing world economic production in 2019 (Stadler et al., 2018) that is used in MORDRED's economic module was modified for the food sector which contains the agricultural sectors. We assume that only part of the production and consumption within the subsistence regime is included in official statistics, and that this monetized subsistence consumption is concentrated in the agricultural sector, reflecting, for example, income earned through selling part of the harvest on the market. This monetized subsistence output is assumed to correspond to the monetized consumption of the subsistence population, which we estimate using an extreme poverty threshold of 2.15 2017-PPP-USD/day. By converting this value into 2019-€ and multiplying it by the initial size of the subsistence population, we derive our estimate of the subsistence output reflected in the IO table. This value is then deducted from the global food sector's output (x_1) (10). In this way, both the subsistence production and consumption have been separated from the global economy.

For simplicity, we assume that the subsistence sector does not rely on any economic inputs from the world economy. Thus, the first column of the A matrix, which contains the input coefficients of the food sector, is modified by multiplying the original values with the ratio between the sectoral output with and without the monetized subsistence output (11).

To remove labor hours of the subsistence population from the global working force, we assume that 70% of the subsistence class works in the food sector and that half of the working day of the subsistence class, i.e. 4 hours, flows into the production of output which enters the formal economy, and, thus, is monetized. The resulting estimated annual hours of subsistence work are subtracted from the original number of annual hours worked in the global food sector (12).

Last, by multiplying the initial land intensity ($Int_{subt_0}^{Land}$) by the size of the subsistence population, the total amount of subsistence land is derived. This value is then subtracted from the sum of cropland and grassland used by the food sector, which is given in the environmental extension of Exiobase3 (13).

$$x_{1\ without\ sub} = x_{1\ with\ sub} - \sum_{r,a} (P_{r,a}^{sub})_{t_0} \cdot Cp_{c_{sub}} \quad (10)$$

$$A_{(without\ sub)} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{1,1} \cdot \frac{x1_{with\ sub}}{x1_{without\ sub}} & \dots & a_{1,25} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{25,1} \cdot \frac{x1_{with\ sub}}{x1_{without\ sub}} & \dots & a_{25,25} \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

$$L1_{without\ sub} = L1_{with\ sub} - (0.7 \cdot \sum_{r,a} (P_{r,a}^{sub}) \cdot \frac{4\ h}{d} \cdot \frac{5\ d}{w} \cdot 49\ w) \quad (12)$$

$$Land_{1,cropland\ \&\ pastures_{without\ sub_{t0}}} = Land_{1,cropland\ \&\ pastures_{t0}} - Land_{sub_{t0}} \quad (13)$$

As a result of these simple operations, the labor and land productivity of the global food sector, as well as its input intensity increase, which is characteristic of industrialized and capitalized agriculture. Thus, MORDRED contains two somewhat artificial economic spheres that change dynamically throughout the simulation, reflecting capitalist expansion as well as incomplete integration into the world economy: The global economic sphere, devoid of any subsistence production and consumption, and the subsistence sphere, devoid of any inputs from the global economy. However, due to the high uncertainty regarding data and estimates about the subsistence sector, we stress that the model outcomes resulting from scenarios involving the subsistence regime should not be interpreted as precise quantitative projections, but rather as theoretical model dynamics that serve exploratory scenario analyses of future rural–urban interactions. The same holds for the ‘urbanization indicator’ (UI), which we added to the model as a measure of the rural poor’s integration into the world economy. The UI is calculated as the ratio between the population linked to the rural area and the total world population (14).

$\alpha_{non-workers}$ multiplies the number of workers with a factor that considers that the workers sustain the non-working population, while $\alpha_{rural\ services}$ is a correction factor that takes into account that there must be a minimum of additional non-agricultural and non-food processing economic activity to avoid rural depopulation, which requires additional workers and dependent non-working population. Both factors can vary according to the scenario.

$$UI = 1 - \left[\frac{\sum_{r,a} (P_{r,a}^{sub}) + \left(\frac{Int_1^{Labor\ hours} \cdot x_1}{annual\ hours\ worked} \right) (\alpha_{non-workers} + \alpha_{rural\ services})}{\sum_{r,a} (P_{r,a}^{sub}) + \sum_{r,a} (P_{r,a}^{we})} \right] \quad (14)$$

Figure 1 provides a graphical representation of the relationships between the world economy and the subsistence regime.

Figure 1: Representation of links between the industrialized global economy and modes of production at its margins in MORDRED. Arrows from the global economy to the outside indicate an expansion of capitalist economic activities, particularly through expanding commodity frontiers. Arrows between the world economy and the subsistence regime indicate inflows and outflows of land and labor that vary according to the simulated scenario. For simplicity, only the land and labor belonging to the subsistence economy are depicted.

2.2. Scenarios

The aim of our scenario exercise is to explore a wide range of conceivable development pathways for the capitalist world economy and the subsistence regime. Therefore, we simulate 4 scenarios (A-D) for the period 2019-2100, which differ in variables influencing subsistence-global economy interactions, while adopting the model's default values for the remaining parameters. Table 1 highlights similarities and differences between the scenarios for selected variables. The numerical values corresponding to the parametrization of these variables are provided in the Supplementary Material. The scenarios are simulated with all scarcity factors activated, except for two mechanisms that ration, and increase the input costs of, fossil extraction, resulting in very high fossil resource availability.

	Scenario A	Scenario B	Scenario C	Scenario D
Technological and economic development	Moderate energy efficiency gains, electrification and changes in electricity mix toward renewables.			
Desired annual per capita consumption growth rate	Center: 1.7% Semiperiphery: Richest 20%: 2.7%; poorest 30%: 3.5%; middle 50%: 3.2% Periphery: Richest 20%: 2.8%; poorest 30%: 3%; middle 50%: 3.1%.	Same as A but: consumption growth rate of the poorest 30% of the semiperiphery and periphery is divided by 10.		

Consumption priorities in the case of scarcity	Investment > center (public and private consumption) > rest of the world.	Investment > poorest 30% of periphery & semiperiphery > governments of all regions & center all households > remaining households.	Investment > governments & households of the center > poorest 30% periphery > poorest 30% semiperiphery > richest 20% and middle class periphery & richest 20% semiperiphery > middle class semiperiphery
Rural-urban migration	High willingness to migrate from the subsistence to the global economy.	Low willingness to migrate from the subsistence to the global economy.	
Labor productivity	High increase driven by learning and technological progress.	Increase is 10% higher than in A.	
Land intensity	Very high reductions driven by learning and technological progress.	High reductions driven by learning and technological progress.	
Land intensity subsistence	Constant.		Increasing due to climate change impacts; decreasing due to adaptation.
Land priorities	World economy > subsistence > natural ecosystems.		
Land availability	Higher land availability due to a lack of land protection.	Protection of 40% of primary forest.	
Fossil fuel availability	Very high .		
Climate damages	No.	Yes.	

Table 1: Similarities and differences in the scenario assumptions of scenarios A-D.

3. Results

In this section, we compare four global futures characterized by different dynamics between the subsistence system and the global economic system, and highlight the key simulation outcomes.

3.1. A: Neoliberal promises

In this scenario, resource scarcity, climate change impacts, and other negative global environmental changes are assumed to be nonexistent or to manifest only in the 22nd century. Consequently, there are no limits to the continued expansion and development of the global capitalist system.

During the first decades, economic growth is supported by an expanding global labor force, driven primarily by population growth within the world economy and by migration from the subsistence regime into the global economy. However, with increasing per capita consumption levels that are facilitated by a continuous growth in global productive capacities, the overall

birth rates in the world economy begin to decline faster than the death rates. Once the majority of the subsistence population has been absorbed into the global labor force, overall labor supply begins to fall, although by 2100 it still remains slightly above the initial level (Figure 2a). Conversely, the productivity of both labor and land grows exponentially throughout the simulation, enabling continuous expansion of global output (Figure 2b). In this scenario, the gap between the consumption levels of the world's poorest classes and those of the subsistence class widens rapidly, creating an incentive to leave subsistence regime. By 2060, the vast majority of the initial subsistence population has migrated, and by the end of the simulation the subsistence sector has disappeared entirely (Figure 2c). As the population living in subsistence declines, land demand decreases accordingly, meaning that the land used for subsistence production follows the same exponential decline (Figure 2d).

Figure 2: Evolution of a) maximum labor supply, b) labor (blue) and land (green) productivity in the food sector, c) population without full integration into the world economy and d) subsistence land in scenario A.

The disappearance of the subsistence sector, combined with large increases in labor productivity in the food sector, leads to a strong rise in the value of the urbanization indicator (Figure 3a). We interpret this as continued dominance of rural-to-urban migration patterns, particularly in peripheral and semiperipheral regions, further reinforcing dynamic urban development.

Global final demand grows steadily, reaching a level by 2100 that is approximately four times higher than at the start of the simulation (Figure 3b). The scenario is replicating the neoliberal narrative that economic growth ultimately benefits all classes: the increase in global final demand is not only driven by elites' consumption expectations but also by all other segments of the world population. As industrialization unfolds with greater strength in the periphery, extreme poverty is eradicated worldwide within four decades. Throughout the scenario, the world's poor, which are soon completely integrated into world economic production processes, experience significant increases in their living standard, especially during the second half of the simulation. In 2060, the poorest 30% of the semiperiphery consume about €5,300 per person per year and those of the periphery about €3,100. These values increase to more than €17,500 and €8,700 respectively by 2100 (Figure 3c). The middle class benefits even more: while the middle 50% of the semiperiphery consume about €11,500 per capita in 2060, by 2100 this

increases to nearly €35,000 annually. In the periphery, middle-class consumption reaches €6,000 per capita by 2060 and almost €17,500 by the end of the simulation.

Despite rapid global economic growth, final demand and household consumption begin to slow toward the end of the simulation. This dynamic results from increasing labor scarcity, as productivity gains fail to keep pace with the shrinking labor supply—driven by population decline and global aging—while consumption expectations rise continuously. Thus, notably, even in a scenario without biophysical constraints, economic growth might still diminish.

Given that scenario A exhibits high economic inequality paired with high economic growth and a considerable improvement in the poor’s consumption levels, we refer to it as *Neoliberal promises*.

Figure 3: Projected evolution of a) the urbanization indicator, b) total annual final demand, c) annual consumption per capita of the poorest 30% of the semiperiphery and periphery; d) annual consumption per capita of the middle 50% of the semiperiphery and periphery in scenario A.

3.2. B: Shadows of neoliberal development

In scenario B, the subsistence population is less willing to migrate, and the consumption of the poorest 30% of the population in the semiperipheral and peripheral parts of the global economy grows very slowly, reflecting barriers for these groups to access employment with a decent salary. Throughout the entire simulation the consumption per capita of the poorest class only grows by 160€ in the periphery and by 280€ in the semiperiphery (Figure 4a).

Annual per capita consumption of the middle class, grows stronger: in the semiperiphery consumption reaches 6,370€ by 2060 and 10,000€/year by 2100; in the periphery, the middle classes consumes less than 5,000€ by the end of the simulation (Figure 4b).

While the low growth in consumption among the poorest classes stems from exogenous scenario assumptions, the lower consumption of the middle classes compared to Scenario A is caused by land scarcity, which emerges relatively early in the simulation, to the detriment of consumption for populations living outside the center. Whereas in Scenario A child mortality rates in the semiperiphery and periphery converge with those of the center by 2060 and 2080, in Scenario B improvements in child mortality are slower, and rates remain higher in the semiperiphery and periphery than in the center until the end of the simulation. The lower consumption levels of the poorer classes result in slower growth of global final demand (Figure 4d).

Figure 4: Per capita consumption of (a) the poorest 30%, (b) the middle 50%; (c) child mortality (calculated with respect to the child mortality rate in the periphery in 2019) and (d) global final demand in scenario B.

The less favorable macroeconomic situation, especially for the most vulnerable population groups within the world economy, reduce the incentives to leave the subsistence sector. Consequently, the population of the subsistence sector in the first 1.5 decades of the simulation declines only by about 200 million people. In 2033, however, there is a turning point after which outmigration accelerates significantly, leading to a faster decline of the subsistence population which drops to 70 million people in 2060 (Figure 5a). This dynamic is driven by the capitalist economy's expansion that leads to increasing demand for land. Due to the limited land availability and the scenario's prioritization of land demand from the world economy over land demand from the subsistence sector, part of the subsistence land is converted into land used by the global economy. Thus, scenario B represents a future featuring strong capitalist accumulation by dispossession: subsistence land is expropriated, capitalized and integrated into the world economy, thereby turning into more 'productive' land. Since land serves as a means of livelihood for the subsistence population, its loss amounts to forced outmigration from the subsistence sector and involuntary integration into capitalist labor markets, fueling accumulation by exploitation. As the subsistence population declines, demand for land decreases, leading to a further reduction in subsistence land (Figure 5b). Further indicators for

accumulation by dispossession are the continuously rising extraction levels for different materials used by the global economy (Figure 5b).

Last, the low growth of the global economy, combined with technological progress and a moderate energy transition leads CO2 emissions to peak and decline moderately. Nevertheless, by the end of the simulation, CO2 emissions are still comparable to initial levels, and contrary to political pledges, far from approaching ‘net zero’ (Dafnomilis et al., 2023), which shows a continued reliance of the global economy on accumulation by contamination.

Consequently, this scenario illustrates what may be termed *Shadows of neoliberal development*.

Figure 5: a) Subsistence population, b) subsistence land, c) annual material extraction for copper (blue), nickel (green), silver (orange), tin (red) and zinc (purple), d) annual anthropogenic CO2 emissions in scenario B.

3.3. C: Breakdown of neoliberal development

Scenario C constitutes a worst-case economic and climate scenario, with outcomes that resemble a *Breakdown of neoliberal development*.

During the first 1.5 decades, the consumption of the poorest classes within the world economy peaks and then starts to decline. This reduces incentives for the subsistence population to migrate and the incorporation of cheap labor from the subsistence regime remains low. However, rising land scarcity forces the integration of subsistence land into the world economy from 2030 onward, which—as in scenario B—generates strong accumulation by dispossession and accumulation by exploitation dynamics between 2030-2040. However, the continuous decline in the consumption level of the poorest 30% in the periphery sparks a first wave of remigration to the subsistence sector from 2040-2070. In the last decade of the simulation, a second wave

follows, as the consumption of the poorest class of the semiperiphery drops to critical levels and no policies of redistribution are implemented (Figure 6a).

Since the subsistence regime cannot absorb the entire population wishing to leave the global economy, the first and second migration waves are accompanied by a sharp increase in deaths in the two world regions, as consumption levels of those unable to migrate fall so low that mortality rates escalate (Figure 6b).

Interestingly, the land productivity in the world economy continues to grow during the entire simulation, although it does so at a much lower rate than in the absence of adverse climate impacts (Figure 6c). Changes in the area of land used by the global food industry (Figure 6d) are a result of changing productivities as well as industry and final demand for products of the food sector. Global sectoral land use peaks after two decades and declines sharply during the last decade of the simulation, reflecting a breakdown of the food sector due to the macroeconomic collapse caused and enforced by the massive outmigration of population.

Figure 6: a) Global subsistence population, b) annual deaths in the global economy by region, c) land productivity of the food sector and d) the size of agricultural land in scenario C.

In scenario C, by 2100 global average temperature has increased by 3 °C compared to the pre-industrial period (Figure 7a). As climate damages multiply, the subsistence sector, unlike the industrialized food sector, experiences a decline in productivity (Figure 7b).

The evolution of subsistence land is highly non-linear during the simulation: it is driven by higher subsistence land demand resulting from the loss of land productivity and the migratory movements from urban to rural areas, while simultaneously constrained by land demand from the global economy. However, as the total output from the world economy begins to fall, more land is freed free and becomes available to the subsistence sector (Figure 7c). As a result of the interactions between socio-economic and environmental changes, the urbanization process slows, stabilizes and eventually reverses (Figure 7d).

Thus, Scenario C illustrates how global climate change could interact with other biophysical limits to growth, combined with diverging consumption inequality and persistent neglect of extreme poverty, to produce migration and population dynamics that may be described as a breakdown of capitalist accumulation and a partial return to the subsistence regime.

Figure 7: a) Subsistence land productivity, b) size of subsistence land, c) urbanization indicator and d) global warming in scenario C.

3.4. D: High adaptive capacity

We denominate Scenario D *High adaptive capacity of subsistence economies* because it attributes greater agency and adaptive capacity to subsistence populations than Scenarios A-C, which portray them as passive victims of global economic and environmental change. This ignores the agency of smallholders and their capacity to influence their futures (Karlin, 2025). The principal difference from Scenario C is that the subsistence population is assumed to possess a high capacity for innovation and adaptation in response to the adverse environmental impacts arising from the productive activities of the world economy.

In Scenario D, the population depending completely on the world economy peaks at over 8 billion in 2042 and afterwards declines continuously to 3.8 billion in 2090 and to 1.7 billion in 2100 (Figure 8a). This strong population loss is caused by both higher mortality rates among poorer population groups in the world economy, and by the eventual outmigration of the poorest workers. The evolution of the subsistence population is comparable to Scenario C but during the first wave of outmigration more people from the world economy can be absorbed, while the second wave occurs with a delay of various years (Figure 8b). As a result of the high adaptive capacity within the subsistence sector, the land productivity loss is smaller than in Scenario C and slows down during the simulation although the temperature increase in both scenarios is comparable (Figure 8c,d).

Figure 8: Evolution of a) the population depending entirely on the global economy, b) the population living outside the global economy, c) the subsistence land productivity and d) global warming in Scenario D.

The demographic changes in the global and the subsistence economy explain the changes in the urbanization indicator (Figure 9a). The dynamic is comparable to Scenario C but the final decline in the indicator's value occurs with a temporal delay. At the same time, due to the lower decline in land productivity, the area of land used by the subsistence sector is smaller than in Scenario C (Figure 9b).

Despite the massive population loss, world final demand continues to increase, implying a continued growth in consumption levels of the world's richer social classes. This dynamic is only reversed during the last decade of the simulation as the outmigration of workers from the semiperiphery leaves the world economy with an insufficient labor supply to maintain the desired level of output (Figure 9c).

Comparing the child mortality index in the global economy with those in the subsistence regime, we find that in the subsistence regime child mortality is considerably higher than in the world economy during the first three decades of the simulation. However, during the last five decades, the child mortality index for the world economy's peripheral regions surpasses that of the subsistence economy multiple times. Toward the end of the simulation, the child mortality index of the semiperipheral regions escalates as well, making the subsistence economy increasingly attractive to vulnerable population groups in the global economy (Figure 9c). Changes in the mortality of older age groups mirror the patterns observed for child mortality.

Introducing higher agency into the scenario simulation, thus, has multiple effects: high adaptive capacity leads to less biophysical constraints to the maximum population size, resulting in more people being absorbed during the first migration wave and less people dying in the world economy, although the difference is rather small. Instead, the land area of the subsistence regime is reduced considerably, which lowers the overall anthropogenic pressure on land. As a result, overall land scarcity is slightly reduced, the land demand from the world economy increases and the world economy grows at a slightly higher rate. This results in higher consumption levels within the global economy and a lower outmigration, at least as long as consumption does not reach critically low levels that cause sudden and sharp increases in

mortality in MORDRED. Thus, a higher adaptive capacity in the subsistence sector has a temporary stabilizing effect on the world economy.

Figure 9: Evolution of a) the urbanization indicator, b) the land used by the subsistence sector, c) world final demand and d) the child mortality index for the population living in subsistence or in the global economy's semiperipheral and peripheral regions in Scenario D.

4. Discussion

The conducted explorative scenario exercise should be regarded as a first attempt to model interactions between capitalist and non-capitalist regimes, as well as urban and rural demographic dynamics within an IAM of medium complexity. Thus, unsurprisingly, our work comes with several limitations and important opportunities for future research.

First, the quality of our quantitative simulations is constrained by existing knowledge and data gaps that reflect the deep uncertainty surrounding contemporary global environmental changes and the relative neglect of non-monetized economic activities in quantitative economic and statistical research. The imbalance in data availability and reliability between high-income and low-income countries necessarily creates biases in our simulations that are difficult to control for. Although a large number of case studies in political ecology exist, and some attempts at quantifying political distribution conflicts have been made (Temper et al., 2018, 2020), a weak state presence in subsistence-dominated areas generally implies less reliable official statistics describing environmental, economic, demographic, cultural and social conditions in territories not subject to the capitalist mode of production. As a result, in addition to general uncertainties regarding the capacity of the global capitalist economy to mitigate, cope with, and adapt to climate change, little is known about the future adaptation capacity and resilience of the subsistence regime, maximum rates of rural re-migration, the rates at which land can be recovered and restored, or the speed at which local and Indigenous knowledge can be recovered and disseminated in scenarios of capitalist breakdown (cf. Aswani et al., 2018; Morton, 2007). Consequently, there is high uncertainty surrounding the more radical scenarios C and D in our scenario exercise. The discontinuous dynamics observable in these scenarios are produced by specific scenario assumptions indicated in the Methods section and the Supplementary Material.

They should not be understood as predictions of unavoidable collapse and ‘ruralization’, but they do question the stability of current trends and structures.

Second, there are limits to the model structure itself stemming from the simplified representation of the subsistence sector. For example, we do not consider gender inequalities or other power structures within subsistence regimes (Jost et al., 2016; Muzari, 2016). Likewise, the model’s dualism, i.e., the creation of two separate spheres—subsistence regime and global economy—linked only through migration flows, cannot capture hybrid agricultural regimes characterized by medium industrial input intensity. The model also cannot reflect the full complexity of rural transformation processes, which may involve additional accumulation dynamics beyond those considered here. For instance, accumulation by assimilation relies on integration under disadvantageous terms rather than dispossession, e.g. through contract farming (Marin-Burgos & Clancy, 2017; Pratama et al., 2021). Moreover, the model does not represent the economic characteristics of the urban informal sector, which plays a key role in maintaining the socio-economic metabolism of many cities in the Global South (Schindler, 2017). In MORDRED, the population engaged in informal economic activities belongs to the lowest consumption classes in the periphery and semi-periphery. Their vulnerability to economic and environmental shocks is reflected in consumption cuts rather than through explicit disruptions of informal production processes.

For these reasons, although our scenario exercise is based on quantitative data, it is best interpreted as a formal, qualitative exploration of multiple complex dynamics that may result in radically divergent rural-urban landscapes. To avoid implying a false level of quantitative precision, we only indicate three reference years (2020, 2060, 2100) in the figures showing simulation results.

In light of these limitations, future work could focus on systematizing existing case studies and surveys to create more coherent and comprehensive databases suitable for modeling rural and urban subsistence and care economies. Likewise, uncertainties could be reduced through the development of new databases focusing specifically on production-related variables in the subsistence sector, including knowledge and technology, energy and material flows, contamination, land productivity, labor productivity and division of work, as well as changes in these variables in response to environmental change.

Equally, modelers could aim to construct IAMs that incorporate differentiated economic structures, including informal and subsistence modes of (re)production, and that integrate model and scenario assumptions beyond neoclassical economic theory. We hold that scenarios introduced in current IAMs focus excessively on ‘neoliberal promises’ depicted in *scenario A*, rather than on the complex and contested urbanization dynamics and their intersections with environmental problems and uneven economic growth that have characterized development in the Global South. Our scenario exercise shows dynamics of accumulation through exploitation, dispossession, and contamination in a relatively simple way, demonstrating that it is possible to build IAMs that reflect critical perspectives on capitalist development and urbanization. It is equally conceivable to combine economic models focused on subsistence, demographic change, and unequal development with energy, emissions, and climate models to enhance their relevance for climate research.

Regarding the content of global environmental scenarios, our simulations open the possibility of futures with radically altered spatial configurations, metabolisms, migration flows, and dominant forms of economic (re)production. While the need for more disruptive and

discontinuous scenarios has already been emphasized elsewhere (Rothman et al., 2023), our scenario development exercise illustrates the importance of reflecting on the (ir)reversibility of urbanization and the (un)desirability of maintaining ways of life and modes of production outside capitalist logics (Gillen et al., 2022; Ridgeway, 2007; Wang, 2024). Actively involving actors from the subsistence sector or the urban informal sector as key stakeholders in the development of global climate, energy, land, and biodiversity scenarios would likely lead to scenarios grounded in everyday experiences and future perceptions that are too often ignored in global environmental scenario analyses, and could yield new insights into poverty reduction, vulnerability, adaptation, resilience, and socio-political mobilization.

5. Conclusion

In this article, we have integrated a simple subsistence sector and migration dynamics between the subsistence sector and the global economy into an IAM to explore different global economic and environmental futures. The scenario exercise points to several highly policy-relevant risks, such as persistent urban poverty, which could be exacerbated by future climate change impacts, and the possibility of large-scale economic breakdown and a reversal of urbanization in worst-case scenarios. Under continued environmental degradation, neoliberal development cannot deliver its promises and may instead lead to profound human suffering and social disruption. The explorative scenario work conducted here therefore highlights the importance of adopting new development paradigms that prioritize poverty eradication, basic human needs, ecological regeneration, and resilience over capital accumulation in both rural and urban contexts. Quantitative models can play an important role in informing political decision-making in this regard, but only if overly idealistic and power-blind neoclassical assumptions are problematized and adapted.

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